

MooringSense – GA 851703

Mooring System Integrity Management through Monitoring, Digital Twin and Control Technologies for Cost Reduction and Increased Efficiency

D8.2 Version 1.0

Communication Plan v2.0

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Executive Summary

This document contains the MooringSense Communication Plan, which has been designed to be in line with the definition provided by the H2020 programme and the contractual obligations. It includes the description of MooringSense communication strategy, the project visual identity and communication material.

Since communication actions and dissemination activities can overlap and make use of the same tools, the present document is complemented with the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan.

To allow continuous Communication Plan adaptation, the initially defined plan will be updated twice along the project duration, in Months 12 and 24. This document is the first update.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Term	Description
B2B	Business to business
EERA	European Energy Research Alliance
EU	European Union
FOW	Floating Offshore Wind
FOWT	Floating Offshore Wind Turbine
H2020	Horizon 2020
INEA	Innovation and Networks Executive Agency
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
JP	Joint Programme
KOM	Kick-Off Meeting
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
OW	Offshore Wind
O&G	Oil and gas
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
RDI	Research, Development and Innovation
R&I	Research and Innovation
SME	Small and medium enterprise
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
URL	Universal Resource Locator
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The effective MooringSense communication requires to set strategic measures to reach a multitude of audiences beyond the project own community (e.g. industrial and scientific communities), including the media and the public in general. At this regard, it is considered of paramount importance to reach out to the European society in order show the impact and benefits of EU-funded research and innovation activities, and how MooringSense addresses societal challenges related to decarbonization and energy security, providing innovative solutions with high impact.

1.1 Purpose and scope

The purpose of the MooringSense's Communication Plan is to define the set of actions and measures, as well as the communication material to be used in the promotion of the project and its results during the whole lifetime of the action. Three versions of the Communication Plan will be elaborated during the project. This document describes the second version of the plan.

The first version of the Communication plan covered the definition of the MooringSense communication strategy, including objectives, message and target audiences, the identification and definition of the intended communication channels and communication materials, the definition of metrics and targets to monitor de effectiveness of the communication activity and a planning of activities.

The second version provides more details on the communication plan definition and reports the main actions and achievements.

1.2 Intended audience / Classification

This document is intended for all project partners, WP leaders and WP participants. The document is also intended for use outside the project, it is therefore classified as a public document.

Relevant parts of this study can however be used in public documents.

1.3 Application documents

Inputs from the following documents were used as a source of information for preparing this document.

Table 1.1: Application documents

REF	Document
AD-01	Grant Agreement – 851703 - MooringSense
AD-02	Consortium Agreement – MooringSense

1.4 Reference documents

The following list contains references to other deliverables of the MooringSense project mentioned in the present document, where complementary information can be found.

Table 1.2: Reference documents

REF	Document
RD-01	D8.6 Communication and Dissemination Report on Activities
RD-02	D8.1 Communication Plan v1

1.5 Document structure

The document is structured in the following sections:

- Section 2 provides a brief description of the methodology.
- Section 3 describes the MooringSense communication strategy through the identification of main objectives, key message, and target audience.
- Section 4 provides detailed information about the commercial material that will be used in the project
- Section 5 details the metrics that will be used for the assessment of communication activities
- Section 6 provides the GANTT of the communication action plan

2. Methodology

In addition to dissemination of MooringSense project results, partners will make a remarkable effort to effectively communicate the project and its impacts. All the communication activities will be accomplished through a specific communication plan that will be designed and implemented within the project. This plan intends to be used by the MooringSense project partners as a guide to develop their individual and collective communication activities according to the communication strategy defined.

The communication plan described in this document comprises a wide variety of measures to ensure the fulfilment of communication objectives, as well as the definition of metrics to enable the communication success assessment.

Finally, the communication plan will be updated along the project to ensure the achievement of communication targets. Plan updates have been scheduled with the following calendar:

Figure 2.1: Communication Plan updates

3. Communication Strategy

3.1 Objectives

The communication strategy of MooringSense project has three main goals:

1. **Project traceability:** Tracing the project implies constantly and coherently communicating its development, the main milestones reached and the most relevant results. Openness has been a priority, but at the same time issues regarding IPR protection will be taken into account.
2. **Broader socialization.** Technological innovations and cost reductions achieved by the European industry has paved the way for the wind energy sector to emerge as a strategic sector for the European economy and for its growth and decarbonization. However, proactive innovation is still needed to keep the EU wind industry's competitive edge and technology innovation efforts. The socialization goals can be stated as:
 - a) EU R&I strategy and MooringSense alignment (e.g. improving operation and maintenance via digitization).
 - b) Public funding leveraged to unlock private investment in R&I.
 - c) Remove barriers regarding social acceptance of FOW.
3. **Raise awareness** of the paramount importance for Europe of wind energy, in particular the OW energy, as a strategic sector for the European economy and for the wellbeing and prosperity of European societies.

The present Communication Plan details the instruments intended to be used by the MooringSense consortium to ensure the above-mentioned goals. Communication activities will be continuously monitored and reported with detail in RD-01 (D8.6 Communication and Dissemination Report on Activities).

3.2 Key message

The key message is that the MooringSense project will help to reduce the cost associated to the production of offshore energy, enhancing the shift from production from fossil to renewable energy sources and contributing to solve the global climate and energy challenges.

Through the development of more efficient strategies and tools for mooring system integrity and control, MooringSense aims at reducing FOW operational costs by 10-15% and to increase the Annual Energy Production by 2-3%.

Key facts/ideas:

- O&M costs in FOW farms can range between 6% and 20% of the whole Life Cycle Cost depending on site conditions and the FOWT technology concept. At the same time, maintenance accounts for the largest portion of O&M effort, cost and risk.
- MooringSense will foster the shift from unscheduled maintenance to schedule maintenance, since scheduled maintenance results in reduced costs of services and optimized availability (less downtime).
- Mooring systems failure statistics in the O&G sector show unexpected high failure rates. From this data, it can be derived that there is a high degree of uncertainty related to mooring systems performance and O&M costs. Even more if we considered the higher complexity of FOWT loading conditions.
- Current control strategies are conservative and control parameters are tuned in a not coordinated way along the wind farm. On the other hand, FOWT components are sized to withstand the worst-case extreme and fatigue loads. If more holistic control strategies were developed and applied it could lead to improved operation of FOW farms and increased efficiency, since an optimal balance between loads and energy production could be reached.

3.3 Target Audience

To ensure the maximum effectiveness of the communication plan, potential interested parties have been identified and grouped, in order to address specific messages via the optimal channels:

Table 3.1: Communication targets and appropriate communication tools

Stakeholders	Objectives [Impact]	Communication Activity/Channel
General public	To raise project awareness [Low]	Visual identity; Website; Infographic video; Brochures, flyers, leaflets; Press releases; Social media: YouTube, Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn. In addition to the above mentioned channels: Public deliverables; Demonstrators; Workshops; In addition to the above mentioned channels: B2B meetings with experts and relevant stakeholders.
Green organizations	To inform about environmental aspects [Medium]	
EU/International associations or platforms in the Energy Sector.	To inform about the latest advancements of research in the field [Medium]	
Governmental agencies & regulatory bodies	To have their support, as their impact is high [High]	
Scientific community	To exchange knowledge, research findings and best practices developed in related projects [High]	
Industry/SME and Advisory Board	Create potential commercialization opportunities with stakeholders [High]	

The main roles of the project target groups are as follows:

Table 3.2: Preliminary Communication Plan

Audience	General public	Green organizations	EU/International associations	Public bodies	Scientific community	Industry/SME and Advisory Board
Increase project visibility	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Give input/feedback on project development	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Generate Market opportunities	X	✓	✓	X	X	✓
Support project development	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Advance Collaboration	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

According to the different target groups and communication objectives identified, the following activities are planned:

- **Objective 1: Improving Competitiveness and Market Uptake**

To WHOM	WHY and WHAT	HOW
Industry-FOW operators and service providers	Inform potential customers about benefits and potentials of the MooringSense development and receive feedbacks from an end-user point of view	Direct contact with end-users in workshops , discussions with the industrial partners (Advisory Board), dedicated information on brochures , website, presentations in relevant European and National associations (EERA JP WIND ...), participation in exhibition events.
Industry - European OW	Increase critical mass on the market, identify potential synergies, foster wider commercialisation of results, establish cooperation relations and maximize and extend project impacts.	Dedicated workshops, conferences and brochures . Participation in EU (Wind Europe, Vanguard Initiative, EERA JP WIND and JP OCEAN) and national associations (e.g. Reoltec, Enermar, Belgian Energy Research Alliance...). MooringSense will participate actively at key conferences and exhibition EU events about Wind Energy.
Industry - Investors, Banks, Insurance	Provide awareness & means for reducing OPEX and life cycle cost efficiency.	Specific meetings with the participation of contractors/investors as Equinor, EDF, Members of the MooringSense Advisory Board: Film Ocean, DNV GL, NREL, Siemens Gamesa and Dragados Offshore in dedicated meetings.

- **Objective 2: Improving Public Perception and Societal image**

To WHOM	WHY and WHAT	HOW
General public - European citizens, Green Organizations, Public Bodies and Scientific community in general.	Make wider community aware of impact of EU research, Energy Union Strategy and the strategic targets related to OW. Improve public image of OW technology. Enable contacts with the project partners.	MooringSense website; press releases; social media (e.g. Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn); project dissemination material; creation of MooringSense infographic video (YouTube, exhibitions...), interviews in local media and science magazines. Links with consortium members' activities for the promotion of scientific culture and new clean energy technologies
Scientific Community - Other R&D initiatives and project consortia	Use synergies, e.g. joint resources; uptake of suitable external developments. Exchange of results in other OW projects, and cooperative work.	Networks and websites, participation in CSAs, joint workshops , cross-project partner networks, joint conferences, cooperation agreements with other H2020 projects.

Scientific Community	Attract young people; Inform about job opportunities; Improve technical skills for under- post-graduate students.	Training material, presentations at universities, twinning projects, internal placements for students, newsletters to target groups and technical public information.
Other sectors	Get information on latest development and available new solutions; Initiate cooperation with other industry sectors such as O&G, offshore aquaculture, or shipping/shipbuilding.	Desk research, networks of the MooringSense partners who are active in other synergetic sectors (e.g. Intecsea, Vicinay and Bridon-Bekaert for O&G, Sintef Ocean for aquaculture and ocean energy, and TNO for environmental issues).

- **Objective 3: Removing external barriers towards application**

To WHOM	WHY and WHAT	HOW
Cross-industry standards (ISO, Class Societies,	Transmit findings and needs of standards to increase critical mass across sectors.	Participation in meetings in standard committees on EU and national level, facing similar challenges & barriers (technical, environmental, social acceptance, etc....)
Research Administration and funding authorities	Ensure consideration of achievements and RDI needs for future research programmes.	Public deliverables and reports to EU associations, contact with national governments

4. Communication Channels and Material

4.1 Visual Identity

In line with the H2020 visual guidelines, a visual identity has been created for the project, comprising a logo and style in different formats.

The logo has been designed as a word-picture-brand, taking into account the planned usage in both printed and digital media. The logo is built around the project name, including a clear symbol of both mooring lines and floating offshore wind turbines.

It is a very recognizable and eye-catching logo, easy to identify and will ease the project identification by the public:

Figure 4.1: MooringSense logo

On the other hand, selected pantone will help the final user to identify the application environment of the developed technology as a marine application. This color palette will be applied to the different documents' templates:

Table 1 MooringSense logo Pantone

	RGB
	151; 182; 217
	106; 137; 187
	45; 77; 139

4.2 Communication Guidelines

4.2.1 INEA communication guidelines

The intention of these guidelines is to maintain coherence and uniformity in our dissemination and at the same time ensure compliance to EU requirements. These guidelines are based on the communication obligations signed on the Grant Agreement.

Mandatory (as in grant agreement)

- Before engaging in a communication activity, the beneficiaries must inform the Coordinator, that will inform the Agency.
- Communication material shall always display the EU emblem prominently. See https://europa.eu/european-union/abouteuropa/legal_notices_en for more information on the use of the European emblem;

Figure 4.2: EU emblem reproductions in black & white, 2 colours white & blue and colour reproduction

- Communication material shall always include the following text:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 851703

- Any communication activity must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the agency, and the Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

4.2.2 MooringSense additional communication guidelines

In addition to the required, recommended and optional guidelines by the Commission, the project has confirmed their own guidelines. When in doubt or in the unexpected case of conflict, Commission guidelines always have priority.

- *Notification prior to dissemination*
All communication activities will be announced prior to dissemination to the Project Coordinator at: WP8@mooringsense.com.
- *Reference to website*
All dissemination activities will refer to the website URL of the project; All project members will ensure that their communication activity or product is also recorded on the MooringSense website: www.mooringsense.eu
- *Compliance to style*
In communication activities where project members present the project or on behalf of the project, all will use the MooringSense house style as much as possible over the affiliations house style (logo, and templates)

4.3 Partners Website

All the partners will include a mention to the MooringSense project and their contribution on their respective websites:

Partner	Website publication
CTC	https://centrotecnologicocctc.com/2019/11/12/mooringsense/
SAITEC	https://www.saitec.es/en/noticias/noticia26.html
ZUNIBAL	https://zunibal.com/en/mooringsense/
TNO	https://www.tno.nl/en (*)
VICINAY	https://www.vicinaymarine.com (*)
IKERLAN	https://www.ikerlan.es/noticias
SINTEF OCEAN	https://www.sintef.no/en/ocean/offshore-wind/#News (*)
BWRI	https://www.bekaert.com (*)
INTECSEA	http://www.intecsea.com (*)

(*) In preparation on the moment of delivery of this deliverable

4.4 Project Website

One of the main communication channels of the MooringSense project is the website. The project website will serve as a central point for all public materials: links to relevant events or publications related to the project, notes about events where consortium members are participating, press releases, news on the field, documentation generated by the project like public deliverables, online versions of any leaflets or posters, and other useful material like possible videos of eventual integration tests. Besides, the main language on the website is English, which facilitates its wider diffusion in the EU.

MooringSense website is available since early March 2020 and it is organized in several sections that are explained hereinafter.

The site will be structured in the following sections and with the following contents:

Table 2 MooringSense website content

HOME
Was designed to act as the main landing page of the website. Consequently, a great effort was paid in the visual design and the use of eye-catching images. Apart from the visual, this page includes key messages for the project and links: updates.

Links to other sections of the website: objectives and technology. Form to subscribe to the MooringSense newsletter.

MooringSense
Objectives

MooringSense aims at reducing FOW operational costs by 10-15% and increasing operational efficiency by means of an increase of Annual Energy Production by 2-3%, through the development of more efficient strategies and tools for mooring system integrity management and control.

[View more →](#)

MooringSense
Technology

MooringSense will take advantage of mooring systems' updated condition information, provided by a Digital Twin (DT) and innovative monitoring technologies, to allow the implementation risk-based integrity management plans and more holistic control strategies to reduce OPEX and increase energy production of FOW farms.

[View more →](#)

Sign up to our newsletter

I accept the [Privacy Policy](#)

[View our newsletter →](#)

Information about the consortium and the main technical contributions of each partners.

MooringSense

The project MooringSense aims at reducing operational costs and increasing efficiency through the development of an efficient risk-based integrity management strategy for mooring systems based on an affordable and reliable on-line monitoring technology.

Consortium

The consortium comprises 9 partners from Europe's key OW industry and academia, including worldwide market leaders in chains (VIC), wires and ropes (BR), both producing hybrid solutions for the mooring lines.

They will collaborate to improve the understanding of mooring lines loading and performance, including a degradation mechanism.

<p>CTC GNSS-sensors and algorithms for marine applications. Materials degradation for Offshore applications.</p> <p>BRIDON BEKAERT Bekaert Wire Rope Industry is the worldwide market leader in wires and ropes for mooring systems.</p> <p>IKERLAN Control systems and Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) systems.</p> <p>INTECSEA Intecsea is an engineering company with a vast track record in O&G and FOW sectors providing support in O&M applied to offshore assets.</p> <p>SAITEC Saitec Offshore Technologies is a Floating wind turbine platform developer. Its role in the MooringSense project is to provide...</p>	<p>SINTEF Coupled Models development and Ocean Basin testing for O&G and FOW.</p> <p>TNO Control systems, O&M planning and cost models.</p> <p>VICINAY MARINE Vicinay Marine Innovation is the Engineering and RDI Company of Vicinay Marine, a worldclass supplier of mooring chains, forged connectors and subsea solutions.</p> <p>ZUNIBAL Development of smart sensor for marine applications.</p>
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Links to the MooringSense videos. It can be seen that the first video is currently available:

Links to news and events

News

News

MooringSense lays the foundation for a model to manage the structural integrity of FOW turbine mooring systems

18 May, 2020 by MooringSense in News

SHARE

News

The World's Largest Floating Wind Farm Is Already Hard at Work

5 February, 2020 by MooringSense in News

SHARE

News

Digital Twins Mature in the North Sea

5 February, 2020 by MooringSense in News

SHARE

Events

Events

GLOBAL OFFSHORE WIND 2020 – 16 – 17 June | Manchester Central | #RUKGOW20

5 February, 2020 by MooringSense in Events

Attend the premier offshore wind event in the world's largest offshore wind market. Experience this exciting sector come to life over two jam-packed days of political keynotes, expert panels, debates, procurement tenders, sector deal updates, disruptive innovation, business partnering, international pavilions, inward delegations and much more.

Links to the social networks

European innovation project to reduce the offshore wind turbines operating costs of by up to 15%

f t in

MooringSense @MooringSense · 1 day ago
 #MooringSense #relatednews
 Governments need to kick-start commercial-scale projects to help drive down the levelised cost of energy (LCOE) from #floatingwind according to industry leaders speaking at the @RE_Windpower Offshore & Floating Wind conference
<https://t.co/0L13Pttt4A>

MooringSense @MooringSense · 5 days ago
 MooringSense developments will leverage a mooring airbrake management strategy. Assisted by decision support tools, the strategy will employ the optimization of turbine control parameters for increased energy production.
 #mooringssystems #offshore #floatingwind #windenergy #H2020 <https://t.co/ev3kewz8fB>

Project Information

Grant agreement ID: **851703**
 Start date: **1 November 2019**
 End date: **31 October 2022**
 Funded under: **H2020-EU.3.3.2**
 Overall budget: **€ 4 197 650**
 EU contribution: **€ 4 197 650**

Publications
 News
 Events

Newsletter

About (about the project):

This tab is organized in three subsections:

- Project main objectives: <https://www.mooringssense.eu/objectives/>

- Technology: <https://www.mooring sense.eu/technology/>
- Consortium description (it will include main contacts for the project): <https://www.mooring sense.eu/consortium/>

MooringSense project

Includes a brief description of the project

- Indication of the Milestones
- Progress - to be updated with project current status, last achievements and next steps <https://www.mooring sense.eu/mooring-sense-stages/>

Publications

Publications tab includes the following sections:

- Communication and dissemination material
- Public deliverables: <https://www.mooring sense.eu/deliverables/>
- Scientific publications: <https://www.mooring sense.eu/scientific-publications/>
- Communication: <https://www.mooring sense.eu/communication/>

News and events

It includes:

- Agenda of congresses, events, workshops related to the MooringSense technologies <https://www.mooring sense.eu/events/>
- News linked to the project and the FOW <https://www.mooring sense.eu/news-from-project/>
- Newsletter <https://www.mooring sense.eu/newsletter/>

Contact

It includes the email address of the project coordinator (info@centrotecnologicocct.com) and the physical address of CTC. Besides, in this tab can be found a form for suggestions that is linked to a dedicated email address (info@mooring sense.eu).

Home About MooringSense Publications News and events Contact us

Project contact

For more information about the project please contact.

Centro Tecnológico CTC
Calle Isabel Torres, nº 1, 39011
Santander, Cantabria

E-mail: info@centrotecnologicocct.com

Phone: +34 942 76 69 76

f t in

Form for your suggestions

Name

Phone Email

Message

I accept the Privacy Policy

Send

Your personal data are incorporated to files for which Centro Tecnológico CTC is responsible, with legal address in Parque Científico y Tecnológico de Cantabria (PCTC) de Calle Isabel Torres nº 1, 39011 Santander, whose purpose is the management of collected data in the forms of the web site, the management of contacts, the execution of commercial communication actions and the response to inquiries and suggestions, being in any case their consent mandatory. If it is not provided, we will not be able to assist your request. These data will be kept indefinitely as long as you do not express your will against it. Your data will not be transferred to any entity without your prior consent. You can exercise the rights of access, rectification, limitation of treatment, deletion, portability, cancellation and revocation of the consent given, by writing a copy of your ID to the abovementioned address or to the email: info@centrotecnologicocct.com. In case of not seeing your rights taken care, you will also be able to submit your claim to the Spanish Agency for Data Protection.

The domain www.mooringssense.eu has been registered and the website will be fully available and fully operative on April 2020. The project’s website will remain available for at least one year after project’s conclusion. Then, the results will be migrated to regular parts of the web communication available to the partners.

4.5 Posters, leaflets, and document templates

As part of the communication material, diverse information tools are considered within the MooringSense project. All these elements are generated in accordance with the Communication Guidelines described in section 4.2 Communication Guidelines

First, templates for the elaboration of reports and technical presentations were developed within the first quarter of the project. Then, a first version of MooringSense’s poster and leaflet were elaborated that are available since June 2020.

Figure 4.3: Initial version of the MooringSense’s poster (left) and MooringSense’s leaflet (right)

A second version of the poster and leaflet will be elaborated including preliminary outcomes of the project.

4.6 Newsletter

Periodic newsletters are being released to subscribers among the target groups and interested public. Subscription to the MooringSense newsletter service can be done through the project website. Newsletters content includes the following aspects:

- Project status update
- Future events where the consortium will participate
- Future events related with the project developments
- News related to the project topics

Figure 4.4: MooringSense’s first newsletter

4.7 Social Networks

Social networks are considered to have the power to achieve a multiplier promotional effect on communication activities. Through them it is possible to establish straight communication channels to interact with the target audience.

To make the best use of the social networks and to increase the impact of communication activity, the MooringSense consortium created profiles on the most relevant social networks. Besides, frequent posts with related news and updates on the project are being created, as a strategy to guarantee the growth of the network and to achieve the maximum impact.

Table 1 MooringSense social network profiles

Channel	Link
FACEBOOK	https://www.facebook.com/MooringSense/

<p>TWITTER</p>	<p>https://twitter.com/MooringSense</p>
<p>LINKEDIN</p>	<p>MooringSense Project group</p> <p>As a first step, a MooringSense group has been created. The main advantage is that we will take advantage of our professional connections to reach a bigger audience from the very beginning.</p>

Also, the following considerations will be taken into account regarding hashtags and tags:

- **Mandatory:**
 - The use of Hashtags and tags referring to the EU is mandatory
 - The mention of the profiles of involved partners is mandatory (those having active profile).

- **Recommended:**
 - Hashtags of key words related to the publication content are recommended

The following table shows the different social networks and their direct links, as well as the different hashtags to be used:

Table 1 Summary of hashtags use policy in MooringSense

Channel	Mandatory	Recommended
FACEBOOK	#H2020 @EU_H2020 @centrotecnologicoCTC @ZunibalSL @TNOresearch @sintefocean @BridonBekaert (SAITEC, IKERLAN and INTECSEA not available)	#mooringsystems #O&M #offshore #floatingwind #windenergy #integritymanagement
TWITTER	#H2020 @EU_H2020 @saitecoffshore @zunibal_SL @TNO_nieuws @IKERLAN_official @SINTEF_Ocean @INTECSEA_WP @BridonBekaert (CTC, VICINAY not available)	#mooringsystems #O&M #offshore #floatingwind #windenergy #integritymanagement
LINKEDIN	#H2020 @EU_H2020 @Centro Tecnológico CTC @Saitec Offshore @Zunibal @TNO @Viciny Marine Innovacion @IKERLAN @Sintef Ocean	#mooringsystems #O&M #offshore #floatingwind #windenergy #sath #integritymanagement

	@Intecsea @Bridon-Bekaert The Ropes GrouP	
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All the partners will follow the mentioned social networks from their respective organizational accounts and will share and recommend the content to promote the MooringSense networks.

4.8 Videos

A [YouTube channel](#) was created to allocate the MooringSense project videos. The videos will have a maximum duration of 3 minutes and will clearly inform stakeholders and the general public about the main goals of the project and its achievements. Given that the videos are intended to address a wider audience, very simple language will be used and the inclusion of subtitles will be considered to enable their diffusion during events or fairs.

At least the following videos are expected:

Video	Content	Status
1	Intended content: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project and consortium presentation - Motivation behind the project - Expected impacts 	Released in September 2020
2	- Including Water Tank tests images (M22)	-
3	- MooringSense solutions integrated and validates (M34)	-

All YouTube video links will be shared using the video showcase EU service¹. By means of this service, videos are added to the EU-funded R&I projects YouTube Playlist² and also they are promoted via the social media channels (@EUScienceInnov - Twitter, Facebook, YouTube).

Furthermore, the videos will also be shared through the social networks.

4.9 Press Releases

With the intention of rising awareness of the MooringSense project by the general public (i.e. European citizens, green organizations, public bodies and scientific community in general), as well as the FOW stakeholders, several press releases are being elaborated throughout the duration of the project.

Press releases are intended to coincide with the project meetings to provide relevant updates on the status and achievements of the project.

Press Release	Main content	Due date month
PR1	Kick off	M1
PR2	MooringSense Architecture	M7
PR3	MooringSense Specification	M12
PR4	Validated Numerical Models and Tank Testing Data	M19
PR5	Validated SHM system prototype	M24
PR6	Decision Support Tool	M30
PR7	Validated Test Execution Result	M36

All partners will publish project results in local and international press: press releases, newsletters in magazines and newspapers etc. Moreover, all beneficiaries will use their own communication portals to include the main information about the project and its results.

Furthermore, the following distribution channels will be exploited by the partners to maximize the impact of the press releases generated:

- Local agencies

A list of local communication agencies will be created and updated during the project development. Press releases will be also sent to these agencies to maximize the impact and to increase the awareness of European citizens.

- EC's media channels:

- <https://horizon-magazine.eu/>
- <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/newsroom/551/>
- <https://cordis.europa.eu/news/en>

So far, press releases linked to the kick-off meeting and the first progress meeting (May 2020) were made. The following figure shows results in both printed and online media.

¹ Calling all EU-funded R&I projects: <http://ec.europa.eu/research/investeuresearch/index.cfm>

² EU-funded R&I projects Play list <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLvpwIjZTs-LjHDvRTqlyjflLeflXDak5er>

Miércoles, 27/11/20
EL DIARIO MONTAÑÉS

ECONOMÍA | 41

PROYECTO EUROPEO LIDERADO POR EL CTC

El consejero de Industria, Francisco Martín, presentó ayer en Copenhague el proyecto europeo 'MooringSense', liderado por el Centro Tecnológico (CTC) que tiene como objetivo incrementar la eficiencia de los aerogeneradores instalados en el mar y conlleva un aumento del 6% de la plantilla. El consejero, en la foto con los miembros del clúster 'Sea of Innovation' Cantabria, aseguró que atravesará 4,1 millones de euros de programas europeos y prevé reducir hasta un 15% el coste de los generadores eólicos 'offshore'. Cantabria cuenta con un stand en la Feria 'WindEurope Offshore'.

MooringSense, un proyecto liderado por CTC, logra reducir el coste de aerogeneradores

D. M.

SANTANDER. El consorcio de MooringSense, un proyecto europeo liderado por el Centro Tecnológico CTC, ha alcanzado los dos primeros hitos que le permiten sentar las bases para definir un nuevo modelo de gestión de los aerogeneradores flotantes, mediante el que aspira a reducir sus costes de mantenimiento y de operación para la generación de energía eólica marina en un 15% y un 10%, respectivamente.

Los dos primeros pasos dados por el consorcio han sido identificar las principales limitaciones y carencias que presentan las tecnologías actuales asociadas a la gestión de la integridad de los sistemas de fondeo y definir el caso de referencia del proyecto que permita evaluar los desarrollos previstos de forma «realista». Seis meses después de su reunión de lanzamiento, los nueve integrantes del consorcio han hecho balance de los progresos conseguidos.

El CTC lidera un proyecto para reducir el coste de aerogeneradores 'offshore'

La iniciativa europea MooringSense plantea una estrategia de gestión más eficiente para las plataformas eólicas flotantes

M. A. SAMPERIO

SANTANDER. El Centro Tecnológico de Cantabria sigue avanzando en proyectos innovadores y va a dar el siguiente paso en una investigación conjunta de carácter europeo que aspira a reducir hasta un 15% el coste de mantenimiento de los aerogeneradores 'offshore', así como a incrementar su eficiencia. Esta iniciativa, denominada MooringSense, se fundamenta en el desarrollo de una estrategia de gestión de la integridad de los sistemas de fondeo más eficiente para las plataformas eólicas flotantes. El proyecto no solo reducirá los costes de operación, sino que optimizará el rendimiento actual que ofrece la energía eólica flotante para aumentar la producción energética anual entre un 2 y un 3%.

La reunión de lanzamiento de este proyecto, cuyo plan de ejecución es de 36 meses, se ha celebrado ayer en Bruselas. Esta primera reunión oficial del proyecto ha sido liderada por el equipo de CTC formado por María Campo-Cosco, responsable del área de Investigación y Robótica, Verónica González de Lena, responsable del área de Industria y Energía, y Alberto Barea, responsable de Desarrollo Tecnológico de CTC. La presentación pública de esta investigación se realizará el próximo 26 de noviembre en el evento WindEurope Offshore 2020, que tendrá lugar en Copenhague y contará con la presencia de Francisco Martín, consejero de Industria de Gobierno de Cantabria. Sáiz, Zambal, Viciny Marine Innovación e Iberka, empresas y

Miembros del consorcio que han acudido a la reunión de lanzamiento. © CTC

centros de investigación de España: TNO e Intertec, entidades de Holanda; Belcat Wind Rope Industry, de Bélgica; y Statoff Cluson, de Noruega, completan el consorcio de un proyecto que cuenta con más de 4 millones de euros de financiación correspondientes al programa de investigación e innovación Horizon 2020 de la Unión Europea.

Importante liderazgo
MooringSense es el proyecto más importante liderado por CTC hasta la fecha. El objetivo establecido por los socios implica la puesta en marcha de varias soluciones tecnológicas innovadoras. El diseño y prototipado de un sensor inteligente de bajo coste para monitorizar el movimiento de las plataformas flotantes o el desarrollo de un modelo virtual de sistema de fondeo de alta fidelidad suponen un desafío

para los socios. Además, se centrará en la definición y ejecución de técnicas de estado de salud estructural (SHM), así como estrategias de control para la gestión de estos componentes.

De hecho, si MooringSense alcanza los objetivos previstos, definirá un nuevo enfoque para la gestión de la integridad de los sistemas de anclaje. Asimismo, se espera que los conocimientos derivados del proyecto generen varias patentes. La puesta en marcha de esta investigación multidisciplinar responderá a la necesidad de gestionar los activos offshore de forma más eficiente para contribuir a la reducción del coste de la energía eólica flotante. Las innovaciones tecnológicas y las reducciones de costes lanzan, allanando el camino para que el sector de la energía eólica emerge como un sector estratégico para la economía continental. Sin embargo, necesita una innovación proactiva para mantener el liderazgo mundial en esta tecnología. Además de la reducción de los costes operativos y el incremento de la eficiencia, el proyecto contempla otros beneficios como la reducción del impacto ambiental en el ciclo de vida de los aerogeneradores o la minimización de los riesgos tecnológicos.

MooringSense es el cuarto proyecto europeo que lidera CTC en los últimos años.

Cuenta con más de 4 millones de euros de financiación del programa Horizon

Evwind, News Menu, offshore, Wind Energy

CTC works to reduce the cost of floating wind turbines by 15%

May 14, 2020 | rev

The MooringSense consortium, a European project led by the CTC Technology Center, has reached the first two milestones that allow it to lay the foundations for defining a new management model for floating wind turbines, by means of which it aspires to reduce its maintenance and of operation for the generation of offshore wind energy by 15% and 10%, respectively.

Figure 4.5: Publication in printed newspaper and online media through press releases in MooringSense

4.10 Workshops

Three workshops, at least, will be organized and conducted during the course of the project. These workshops will be scheduled and organized as side events at relevant international events or at MooringSense progress meetings.

Some topics has been already identified together with tentative dates:

1. Mooring system digital twin and model testing (M18)
2. Mooring systems integrity management under risk-based approach (M24).
3. Virtual mooring line tension measurement and SHM. (M30)
4. Final workshop: MooringSense solutions, tools and impacts (M35)

4.11 Publications and participation in events

Scientific publications and the participation of MooringSense's consortium in international events will be key dissemination activities. However, this kind of activities can maximize the impact of communication. A preliminary list of publications and participations in congresses is included below:

Highlights of planned dissemination channels			
Event/Journal	Countries addressed	Type of Audience	Date (planned or expected)
Floating Offshore. Wind Turbine Conference	Global	Floating Offshore Wind	2021-2023
Offshore Energy Exhibition and Conference	Europe	O&G, OW, marine energy	2021-2023
RINA - Royal Institution of Naval Architects	Europe	Marine vessels and structures	2023
OMAE Conference on Ocean, Offshore & Arctic Engineering	Global	Ocean and offshore engineering	2022
OTC - Offshore Technology Conference	Global	Offshore energy	2021
Wind Energy	Global		2023
Ocean Engineering. ISSN: 0029-8018	Global	Offshore platforms. Moorings	2022
Applied Ocean Research ISSN 0141-1187	Global	Floating system hydrodynamics	2023
Journal of Ocean Engineering and Marine Energy. ISSN: 2198-6452	Global	Coastal and offshore engineering, marine renewable energy	2023
WindEurope Conference & Exhibition	Europe	Wind Energy	2021-2023
Journal on Environmental Degradation of Materials and its Control. ISSN: 0010-938X	Global	Corrosion and its control	2022
Marine Structures. ISSN: 0951-8339	Global	Design, fabrication and O&M	2023
GPS Solutions. ISSN 1521-1886	Global	GNSS solutions	2023
The Jo. of Navigation. ISSN 1469-7785	Global	Navigation systems	2022
IAIN Institutes of Navigation	Global	Navigation systems	2023
IEEE/ION-PLANS Position Location and Navigation Symposium	Global	Navigation systems and applications	2022
ICL-GNSS Localization and GNSS	Europe	GNSS solutions and systems	2021
TORQUE	Europe	Wind Energy	2022
Wind Energy Science Conference	Europe	Wind Energy	2021, 2023

EERA-JP WIND	Europe	Wind Energy Association	2021-2023
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Figure 4.6: Participation of Bridon Wire Rope Industry in the Future of Renewables Global 2020 (left). Presentation of the MooringSense project at the WindEurope Offshore in Copenhagen by CTC.

5. Metrics

Regarding communication activity, measurable target results have been defined:

Communication Activity	Channel	Target Metric	Updated Metrics (M12)
Visual Identity	Logo and templates	1 of each	Done
Website	Project Website	>5000 visitors	74 visitors 258 pages visited (*)
Posters and Leaflets	Posters	≥3	1
	Printed Leaflets	>500 leaflets distributed	0
Newsletters	Newsletters	≥6	1
Social Networks	Facebook	>200 followers	36
		>20 posts	120
	Twitter	>200 followers >20 posts	42 119
Videos	YouTube channel	>100 members	180
		>20 posts	110
Press Releases	Press releases in printed and web media	>20	34
Workshops	Side/parallel events at international conferences or progress meetings	≥3	1 st workshop to be celebrated in September 2021
Advisory Board meetings	Side events during MooringSense progress meetings	≥3	1

(*) Data analysis from October 20 to November 5, 2020

